

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

TISSUE CULTURE

Influence of position of rice anthers at plating on callusing and plant regeneration

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We studied the effect of anther orientation at plating on callusing response and plant regeneration in japonica rice variety Taipei 309. Callus induction from anthers was according to standard IRRI procedure.

Anthers were plated on semisolid E10 (modified B5 medium, each liter containing 1 mg 2,4-D, 0.5 mg BAP, 0.5 mg IAA, 20 g sucrose, and 5 g glucose). Sixty anthers were inoculated at random (specific positioning of anthers is extremely difficult because of their small size). Microscopic examination showed that anthers were naturally positioned approximately half on edge (one lobe touching the medium) and half flat (both lobes in contact with the medium).

Plates were incubated at 26-29 °C in dim light and scored for callusing 40 d after plating. Some calli of both flat and edge-oriented anthers were transferred for regeneration in MS medium (1 mg each NAA and kinetin/liter and 30 g sucrose/liter) under continuous light. Percentage of green plant regeneration was recorded.

Most of the anthers dehisced within 5 d of plating, liberating a large part of the pollen grains on the medium. None of the liberated pollen grains developed into calli. Calli from pollen grains held within the anther started appearing about 25 d after inoculation.

Callusing response of anthers. 1 = Anther positioned on edge callusing from upper lobe. 2 = One anther on edge at left and the other flat at right, both callusing. 3 = Anther flat, callusing from both lobes. 4 = Anther flat, callusing from only one lobe. 5 = Anther on edge, callusing from upper and lower lobes. 6 = Anther on edge, callusing from lower lobe only. Note calli from lower lobes growing into the medium.

Of the 2,160 anthers plated, 518 (24%) produced calli. Of the anthers with calli, 60% were plated on edge (see figure) and 40% flat. Most of the anthers plated flat callused on both lobes, but callusing on one lobe was also observed. Most anthers plated on edge produced callus on the upper lobe. Only rarely did anthers plated on edge produce callus from both lobes or from the lower lobe only.

About 15% of the calli transferred for regeneration produced green or green and albino plantlets.

Observations made on rice varieties IR5, Basmati 370, and Pankaj showed the same anther callusing response.

No special anther inoculation technique is needed to get satisfactory callusing response in rice except to see that anthers are not buried in the medium. □